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Dynamic sub-grid models extension

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Executive Summary

waLBerla[1][2] is a software package which allows to perform highly optimized Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations with Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM) on heterogeneous hardware infrastructures. This code is freely available from the [waLBerla official website](#)², where extensive documentation and introductory material are provided.

This report presents the work carried out to improve the capabilities of this software package to simulate complex industrial cases requiring an accurate description of highly turbulent flows in the weakly compressible regime, with great computational efficiency.

The following document is organized as follows. In Section 1, we begin with a short overview of the general issues encountered in Lattice Boltzmann simulations of highly turbulent flows and we provide a detailed discussion of the Recursive Regularized collision operator we have implemented in the Widely Applicable Lattice Boltzmann solver from ERLangen (waLBerla) application to simulate high Reynolds-number flow conditions. We then benchmark the numerical efficiency and the physical accuracy of this approach by carrying out Direct Numerical Simulations (DNS) of simple test-cases like the flow in a three dimensional lid driven cavity and the wake past a sphere in the subcritical regime.

In Section 2, we introduce the concept of Large Eddy Simulations (LES) within LBM calculations, providing a general overview of the approaches available in the literature to model the unresolved scales of the flow. We then focus our attention on Shear Improved Smagorinsky model (SISM), i.e. the subgrid model we have implemented in waLBerla package and coupled with the advanced collision operator discussed in Section 1.

This approach has been then adopted to simulate the airwake of a SFS2 (Simple Frigate Shape 2) ship model in head-wind conditions, whose accurate description is of fundamental importance for an improved modelling of helicopters' ship deck landing operations. Numerical results have been then carefully compared with wind tunnel experimental data available in the literature to assess the accuracy of the implemented methodology in the description of these flows.

Lastly, in Section 3 we describe a set of optimizations we have introduced in waLBerla framework to enhance the numerical efficiency of the code in the simulation of highly turbulent flows on Graphical Processing Unit (GPU). This activity has been mainly focused on improving the code performance when making use of nonuniform Cartesian grids which are mandatory in the case of high Reynolds flows as they strongly reduce the computational effort required by uniform grids to achieve the same level of spatial resolution.

The theoretical methods and the numerical optimizations discussed in this document have been implemented in a modified version of waLBerla, which is available in a [GitHub repository](#)³.

²<https://walberla.net/>

³https://github.com/multixscale/RR-BGK_SISM_waLBerla/

1 Recursive Regularized BGK collision model

Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM) has become a widely used approach to solve computational fluid mechanics problems in a wide variety of fields[3], from transient blood flow simulations[4] to transport modelling in porous media[5]. In this work we focus our attention on the application of LBM approach to the simulation of turbulent flows in the weakly compressible regime. Our aim is to extend the capabilities of the open-source code `waLBerla` to treat this kind of problems, combining an accurate description of the flow physics with numerically-optimized implementations, in order to bring LBM simulations of turbulent flows at the exascale.

The simulation of high Reynolds (Re) flows within LBM is an extremely delicate task. The most famous (and still widely used) collision model in LBM is the single-relaxation-time BGK approach[6][7][8][9]. In this model, the collision operator describes the relaxation of all the Particle Distribution Functions (PDFs) with the same relaxation time τ , which is univocally determined by the kinematic viscosity of the fluid. Despite Chapman-Enskog analysis[10] of BGK-LBM permits to recover Navier-Stokes (NS) equations in the weakly compressible regime[6], this collision model exhibits instability issues for flows at large Reynolds number, as the model becomes progressively unable to properly dissipate non-hydrodynamic modes in the computational domain while increasing Re .

Many advanced collision methods have been formulated to properly solve these issues. Among them, we mention the selective viscosity filter approach proposed by Ricot *et al.*[11], (available in the `LaBS` code) and the cumulant LBM proposed by Geier *et al.*[12], which is already available in `waLBerla`. This second method is purely local, i.e. the collision on one lattice node does not require data from neighboring cells as Ricot's collision, therefore is particularly suited for implementation on GPU architectures[13].

However, cumulant LBM is theoretically formulated only for a D3Q27 lattice, which is less computationally efficient and more memory-demanding than the common D3Q19 stencil, which is in turn able to properly recover NS equations in the low-compressibility regime.

In this work we have implemented the Recursive Regularized BGK (RR-BGK) collision model within the `waLBerla` framework. This method has been initially formulated for a D3Q27 stencil by Malaspinas[14]⁴ and then adapted to a D3Q19 lattice by Jacob and co-workers[16]. We point out that a further improvement of this model (named Hybrid-RR-BGK) has been also presented in Ref.[16]: this method enables an efficient damping of spurious modes caused by grid transitions in vertex-centered nonuniform grids, but it requires non-local computations in the collision process, therefore it has not been considered in the following[17]. A detailed comparison between different regularization approaches is provided in Ref.[18].

We now provide a brief description of this collision model and how it is implemented in practice: more details can be found for example in Ref.[19].

Under the hypothesis of small Knudsen (Kn) number and considering an infinite velocity set, it is possible to split the continuous distribution function $f(\mathbf{x}, \xi, t)$ (where ξ is the continuous velocity) as

$$f(\mathbf{x}, \xi, t) = f^{eq}(\mathbf{x}, \xi, t) + f^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \xi, t) \quad (1)$$

where the non-equilibrium component $f^{(1)}$ is a perturbation of the equilibrium part f^{eq} , if $Kn \ll 1$. The function $f^{(1)}$ is developed on the complete basis of Hermite polynomial tensors $\mathbf{H}^{(n)}$, i.e.

$$f^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \xi, t) = \omega(\xi) \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!c_s^{2n}} \mathbf{a}_1^{(n)}(\mathbf{x}, t) : \mathbf{H}^{(n)}(\xi) \quad (2)$$

where $\omega(\xi)$ is a Gaussian function, $\mathbf{a}_1^{(n)}$ are the projections of $f^{(1)}$ on the n^{th} order Hermite tensor $\mathbf{H}^{(n)}$ and c_s is the speed of sound. Terms of order $n = [0, 1]$ are not included as they are zero by mass and momentum conservation. Applying the Chapman-Enskog analysis to the continuous Boltzmann Equation and using Equation 2 under the hypothesis $f^{(1)} \ll f^{eq}$, it is possible to demonstrate that the coefficients $\mathbf{a}_1^{(n)}$ are fully determined by terms $\mathbf{a}_1^{(n-1)}$ and $\mathbf{a}_1^{(2)}$, if $n \geq 3$; for example, in the case $n = 3$ we have

$$a_{1,\alpha\beta\gamma}^{(3)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = u_\alpha(\mathbf{x}, t) a_{1,\beta\gamma}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, t) + u_\beta(\mathbf{x}, t) a_{1,\alpha\gamma}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, t) + u_\gamma(\mathbf{x}, t) a_{1,\alpha\beta}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (3)$$

being (α, β, γ) cartesian indices and u_α the components of the velocity in the lattice node \mathbf{x} at time t . The recursive formulas for higher order coefficients can be found in Refs. [14][15].

Assuming a discrete velocity set, the basic idea of RR-BGK is to reconstruct the nonequilibrium part of the PDFs so that their projections onto Hermite polynomial tensors satisfy the recursive relations obtained above via Chapman-Enskog

⁴The generalization to compressible flows of Recursive Regularized collision is detailed in Ref.[15].

analysis in the continuous case. For the D3Q19 lattice, the quantities $f_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ are evaluated as

$$f_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = w_i \left[\frac{1}{2c_s^4} \mathbf{a}_1^{(2)} : \mathbf{H}_i^{(2)} + A_1^+ \left(\mathbf{H}_{xxy,i}^{(3)} + \mathbf{H}_{yzz,i}^{(3)} \right) + A_1^- \left(\mathbf{H}_{xxy,i}^{(3)} - \mathbf{H}_{yzz,i}^{(3)} \right) + A_2^+ \left(\mathbf{H}_{xzz,i}^{(3)} + \mathbf{H}_{xyy,i}^{(3)} \right) + A_2^- \left(\mathbf{H}_{xzz,i}^{(3)} - \mathbf{H}_{xyy,i}^{(3)} \right) + A_3^+ \left(\mathbf{H}_{yyz,i}^{(3)} + \mathbf{H}_{xxz,i}^{(3)} \right) + A_3^- \left(\mathbf{H}_{yyz,i}^{(3)} - \mathbf{H}_{xxz,i}^{(3)} \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

where i is an index running over the discrete velocities of the D3Q19 lattice, each with weight w_i . Hermite polynomials of order larger than three and terms $\mathbf{H}_{\alpha\alpha\alpha,i}^{(3)}$ are not considered as they cannot be properly represented by the D3Q19 quadrature. Furthermore, the combinations of third order polynomials appearing in Equation 4 are chosen to guarantee their mutual orthogonality on the D3Q19 lattice.

To reconstruct the non-equilibrium part of the PDFs using from Equation 4, the second order coefficients $\mathbf{a}_1^{(2)}$ are evaluated by projection, using the known on-site pre-collision populations $f_i(\mathbf{x}, t)$ at time t , i.e.

$$a_{1,\alpha\beta}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_i H_{\alpha\beta,i}^{(2)} \left[f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) - f_i^{eq}(\mathbf{x}, t) \right] \quad (5)$$

being f_i^{eq} the discrete equilibrium distribution function developed on the same set of Hermite tensor chosen in Equation 4 and $H_{\alpha\beta,i}^{(2)}$ the (α, β) components of the second order Hermite tensor computed at the discrete velocity \mathbf{c}_i of the i^{th} velocity of the D3Q19 stencil.

The third order coefficients A_I^\pm are computed so that the following relations are fulfilled

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_i f_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{H}_{xxy,i}^{(3)} &= a_{1,xxy}^{(3)}(\mathbf{x}, t) & \sum_i f_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{H}_{xzz,i}^{(3)} &= a_{1,xzz}^{(3)}(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ \sum_i f_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{H}_{yyz,i}^{(3)} &= a_{1,yyz}^{(3)}(\mathbf{x}, t) & \sum_i f_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{H}_{yzz,i}^{(3)} &= a_{1,yzz}^{(3)}(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ \sum_i f_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{H}_{xyy,i}^{(3)} &= a_{1,xyy}^{(3)}(\mathbf{x}, t) & \sum_i f_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{H}_{xxz,i}^{(3)} &= a_{1,xxz}^{(3)}(\mathbf{x}, t) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where third order Hermite projections $a_{1,\alpha\beta\gamma}^{(3)}$ are evaluated using the recursive formula given by Equation 3.

The complete procedure representing the RR-BGK stream-collide algorithm can be therefore summarized with the following steps, to be repeated for each velocity i , at each lattice node \mathbf{x} and for every timestep t .

1. Load from memory the pre-collision populations $f_i(\mathbf{x}, t)$;
2. compute the density ρ and the velocity \mathbf{u} at the node \mathbf{x} starting from $f_i(\mathbf{x}, t)$;
3. compute the equilibrium distribution functions f_i^{eq} using ρ and \mathbf{u} ;
4. evaluate $a_{\alpha\beta}^{(2)}$ using Equation 5;
5. compute coefficients A_I^\pm from Equation 6, making use of the recursive formula provided by Equation 3;
6. compute the reconstructed nonequilibrium populations $f_i^{(1)}$ via Equation 4 and evaluate the collision operator using BGK model as

$$\Omega_i(\mathbf{x}, t) = -\frac{f_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\tau}$$

7. compute post-collision populations f_i^* as

$$f_i^*(\mathbf{x}, t) = f_i^{eq}(\mathbf{x}, t) + \Omega_i(\mathbf{x}, t)$$

To enhance the stability of this method, we also enforce a traceless stress tensor to increase the damping of spurious pressure waves in the computational domain, as proposed by Farag *et al.*[20].

This method has been implemented in waLBer1a source code and it is directly available for usage on NVIDIA GPU hardware[21].

To improve the numerical conditioning of this algorithm (i.e. to reduce its sensitivity to round-off errors caused by finite precision arithmetic), the implementation has been carried out working with weighted-centered distributions $\tilde{f}_i(\mathbf{x}, t) = f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) - w_i$ as suggested by Skordos[22]. In all the calculations we have used double precision floating point accuracy and an Esoteric Twist in-place streaming algorithm[23].

1.1 Testing of numerical efficiency and physical accuracy of RR-BGK collision model

We have started testing the implementation efficiency on GPU of the stream-collide algorithm, adapted to the RR-BGK collision model. All the calculations presented in the the following have been performed on daVinci1 cluster at Leonardo, where GPU units are based on the Nvidia A100 architecture.

We have considered *single-GPU* calculations of the flow in a three dimensional lid driven cavity at $Re = 10^3$, fixing the lid velocity along x direction to 0.05 in lattice units. The interior of the cavity has been meshed with a uniform cubic cartesian mesh, completely contained in a single domain block. This choice ensures to measure the numerical efficiency of the sole stream-collide algorithm by removing the presence of inter-block communications which clearly affect the computational performance of the code.

In Figure 1, we present the number of billion lattice updates per second (GLUPS) obtained for different mesh sizes in the case of RR-BGK collision (blue circles) and for classical BGK model (red triangles): the stream-collide implementation of BGK collision has been obtained via the code-generation functionalities provided by waLBer1a package[24], which guarantee to obtain high performance kernels for different GPU architectures. We notice that the number of Giga Lattice Updates Per Second (GLUPS) converge to about 3.2 once the mesh is sufficiently large (i.e. with more than 256 cells per cavity side) for both collision models, with RR-BGK being only less than 0.05 % slower than the BGK implementation. This result confirms that the actual implementation of RR-BGK offers the same computational efficiency of BGK collision model, while providing better stability properties[25][26].

Figure 1: GLUPS evaluated for different number of lattice nodes along the side of the cubic lid driven cavity. Red circles (blue triangles) are the results obtained via BGK (RR-BGK) collision model. In the inset the velocity magnitude normalized to the lid velocity is displayed in the central plane of the cavity, assuming $Re = 10^3$.

To verify the implementation correctness and the physical accuracy of RR-BGK collision model, we have then considered the flow over a sphere both in the low- Re , steady regime and at $Re = 3700$, when a turbulent unsteady wake after the sphere is expected. We point out that the Reynolds number is here evaluated in terms of the incoming free stream velocity and the sphere diameter.⁵

In all the simulations, we have considered a sphere with diameter D of 2 cm immersed in air at ambient conditions. The sizes of the computational domain have been chosen equal to $22.5D$ along the streamwise direction x and to $14.6D$ along the directions orthogonal to the main flow, with the sphere placed at $6.5D$ from the inflow wall and centered along y and z directions.

The surface of the sphere has been modelled as a no-slip wall, using bounce-back boundary conditions. At the inlet, a fixed velocity has been applied using bounce-back boundary condition with Ladd's correction[6][28], while all the remaining faces of the computational domain have been taken as free slip walls, apart from the outflow where Geier's extrapolation boundary condition[12] has been applied.

In the low Re simulations a sampling of 0.00875 cm has been used, adopting five levels of refinement in the simulation. In Figure 2a, we show the drag coefficient C_d obtained with RR-BGK collision model in waLBer1a (red dots on the dashed line) at different Re numbers, in the range from 100 to 200. Drag coefficients have been computed from the overall drag force exerted on the sphere along the streamwise direction, which has been computed through the Momentum Exchange Method[6] we have implemented as a post-processing functionality in waLBer1a[27]. Our results are in excellent agreement with the data by Tabata and Itakura[29] (green squares in Figure 2a), confirming the correctness of our implementation.

The flow past a sphere at Re equal to 3700 is a widely studied case, both from an experimental and a computational point of view. Here we consider these conditions to check the stability of pure RR-BGK (i.e. without any subgrid scale

⁵The code used to run these benchmarks can be found in [27].

model) to simulate the flow in a regime where classical BGK collision starts showing spurious effects due to poor numerical stability, as demonstrated by Geier *et al.* in Ref.[12].

The computational domain has been chosen equal to the one discussed in the low Re simulations. In Figure 2b, we display the domain decomposition with overall 6 levels of refinement used in the converged calculations (blocks with the same color belong to the same refinement level). The simulation has been performed for 4.5 seconds of physical time, while the drag coefficient has been computed averaging the instantaneous C_d over the last half a second. In Figure 2c we present the instantaneous behaviour of C_d for different near wall samplings. We notice that using six levels of refinement we have been able to achieve a mesh size Δx equal to 0.00309 cm close to the sphere surface, at which the time-averaged C_d converges to 0.39251 which is in very good agreement with the reference value of 0.392 obtained via PaLabos LBM code[30], demonstrating the physical accuracy achieved via RR-BGK collision.

Finally, in Figure 2d we also show the instantaneous velocity field magnitude (normalized by the free stream velocity) at time $t = 4.5$ s: looking at the details of the flow field, it is immediate to notice the absence of spurious numerical waves observed in BGK calculations by Geier, indicating good stability properties of RR-BGK collision model.

Figure 2: Simulation of the flow past a sphere with RR-BGK as implemented in waLBerla code. (a) shows the drag coefficient C_d as a function of the Re number in the interval from 100 to 200, where the flow is stationary: red dots (connected by the dashed line) are the values computed with waLBerla, while green squares are reference data taken from Ref.[29]. In (b) the block-domain-decomposition with six levels of refinement used in the calculation at $Re = 3700$ is presented: different colors correspond to blocks belonging to different refinement levels. (c) Drag coefficient as a function of time at $Re = 3700$ for different near wall samplings. The dashed black line represents the value $C_d = 0.392$ provided in Ref.[30]. (d) Instantaneous velocity magnitude normalized by free-stream velocity in the last timestep of the simulation, at $t = 4.5$ s.

2 Implementation of Shear Improved Smagorinsky Model in waLBerla

In DNS of turbulent flows, all spatial and temporal scales must be numerically resolved; as a consequence, the computational resources required by these simulations grow exponentially with the Reynolds number, making them unfeasible for practical calculations on industrial flows.

In LES, only the larger scales of the flow are explicitly evaluated numerically, while small scale eddies are treated via a modelling approach. The reason for this separation derives from the fact that largest scale eddies carry the majority of the flow's kinetic energy and are highly influenced by the external flow conditions, while small scales have mainly an energy dissipative role and a nearly universal, flow-independent character. In this methodology, large scale features of the flow are extracted via a filtering procedure[31]

$$\bar{\Psi}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \int d\mathbf{x}' G_{\Delta}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}'; t) \Psi(\mathbf{x}', t) \quad (7)$$

being G_{Δ} the filter operator with Δ the size of the characteristic small scales, while Ψ is a general hydrodynamic quantity (like density, velocity or pressure) and $\bar{\Psi}$ is its filtered counterpart.

Navier-Stokes equations for the filtered velocity $\bar{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ are characterized by an additional contribution to the shear stress tensor τ , which accounts for the effect of the small-unresolved scales. In eddy viscosity models, this additional subgrid stress contribution is evaluated as (assuming incompressible fluids)[31][32]

$$\tau_{\alpha\beta}^{sgs}(\mathbf{x}, t) = -2\nu_{sgs}(\mathbf{x}, t) S_{\alpha\beta}(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (8)$$

where $S_{\alpha\beta}$ are the (α, β) components of the strain rate tensor computed from resolved velocities, while $\nu_{sgs}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the subgrid-scale viscosity.

As formally discussed by Malaspinas and Sagaut[33], the subgrid viscosity can be incorporated in BGK collision model in a straightforward way: given $\nu_{sgs}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ at each lattice node, this subgrid viscosity is added to the molecular viscosity ν_{Mol} to compute an effective relaxation time

$$\tau^{eff}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{1}{c_s^2} \left(\nu_{Mol} + \nu_{sgs}(\mathbf{x}, t) \right) + \frac{1}{2} \quad (9)$$

which is directly used in the collision step in each LBM timestep. Many viscosity models have been deeply studied and tested in the framework of LBM simulations[34]. Among these, Smagorinsky (SM) subgrid model[35] has been widely used because of its simplicity in terms of numerical implementation[36]. In SM model, the subgrid viscosity is evaluated as

$$\nu_{sgs}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \left(C_S \Delta \right)^2 \|\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{x}, t)\| \quad (10)$$

where C_S is the Smagorinsky constant, Δ is the local spatial sampling and $\|\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{x}, t)\| = \sqrt{2S_{\alpha\beta}S_{\alpha\beta}}$ is the Frobenius norm of the resolved strain rate tensor at point \mathbf{x} . SM model is particularly suited for LBM calculations as $S_{\alpha\beta}$ can be locally computed from the non-equilibrium part of the PDFs, without evaluating velocity gradients via finite difference which requires non-local operations and more complex communications schemes in parallel computations.

The main limitation of SM model is its excessive dissipative character in wall bounded flows as the subgrid viscosity $\nu_{sgs}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ has finite, non-zero values in the viscous layer close to walls where the flow has a laminar character and the subgrid viscosity is expected to be negligible.

In this work we have implemented a different subgrid viscosity model in waLBerla, i.e., SISM[37][21]. While keeping the numerical efficiency of SM model, SISM is able to remove the near wall unphysical dissipation associated with classical Smagorinsky subgrid viscosity model.

In SISM, the subgrid viscosity is computed as

$$\nu_{sgs}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \left(C_S \Delta \right)^2 \left[\|\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{x}, t)\| - \|\langle \mathbf{S} \rangle(\mathbf{x}, t)\| \right] \quad (11)$$

where C_S has been kept fixed to 0.15 in the following, while $\langle \mathbf{S} \rangle$ is the low frequency component of the strain rate tensor evaluated at point \mathbf{x} . As $\|\langle \mathbf{S} \rangle\|$ is non-zero in the viscous layer, once subtracted to $\|\mathbf{S}\|$, it reduces the value of ν_{sgs} close to walls, solving the near wall issues of SM model discussed above. At the same time, far from walls, $\|\langle \mathbf{S} \rangle\|$ become negligible and the SM viscosity is properly recovered.

This treatment has been directly coupled with the RR-BGK collision model discussed in Section 1. Starting from the the projections of the PDFs on second order Hermite tensors $\mathbf{a}_1^{(2)}$, the strain rate tensor can be locally computed via

$$S_{\alpha\beta}(\mathbf{x}, t) = -\frac{a_{1,\alpha\beta}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, t)}{2\tau_{Mol}\rho c_s^2} \quad (12)$$

where τ_{Mol} is the relaxation frequency associated to the molecular viscosity and ρ is the zero order momentum of the PDFs. Once the instantaneous $S_{\alpha\beta}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is known at each cell \mathbf{x} , the term $\langle \mathbf{S} \rangle$ is evaluated via a temporal moving-average procedure, i.e.

$$\langle S_{\alpha\beta} \rangle(\mathbf{x}, t_n) = \langle S_{\alpha\beta} \rangle(\mathbf{x}, t_{n-1}) + \frac{1}{n+1} \left[S_{\alpha\beta}(\mathbf{x}, t_n) - \langle S_{\alpha\beta} \rangle(\mathbf{x}, t_n) \right] \quad (13)$$

for each discrete timestep $t_n = n\Delta t$ and choosing as initial condition $\langle S_{\alpha\beta} \rangle(\mathbf{x}, t_0) = S_{\alpha\beta}(\mathbf{x}, t_0)$. Finally, using Equations 12 and 13 in Equation 11, the SISM subgrid viscosity is computed and the effective relaxation time τ^{eff} is evaluated via Equation 9 and used to evaluate the collision operator $\Omega_i(\mathbf{x}, t)$ as discussed in Section 1. We point out that other methods have been developed in the literature to compute $\langle S_{\alpha\beta} \rangle$, mainly based on Kalman Filtering technique[38][39]. Here, we decided not to follow this methodology as this procedure requires the evaluation of $\langle S_{\alpha\beta} \rangle$ via finite-differencing of Kalman filtered velocities, reducing the numerical performance of the code as discussed before. Further investigations on this particular aspect are left for future work.

2.1 Application of RR-BGK with SISM model to ship airwake simulations

The coupled implementation combining RR-BGK collision with SISM model for the subgrid viscosity has been applied to simulate the turbulent flow past a Simple Frigate Shape 2 (SFS2) ship model, a highly simplified geometry which is widely used both experimentally and theoretically to investigate the unsteady wake of realistic ships. A proper characterization of these turbulent flows is of fundamental relevance to properly model helicopter's ship deck landing operations and is the starting point for an accurate evaluation of the ship wake effect on the helicopter rotor flow. In the following, we focus on the flow past a 1:100 SFS2 scale model (shown in Figure 3a) in headwind conditions which has been studied in wind tunnel experiments. The code used for running this test-case can be found in [40].

Figure 3: (a) SFS2 ship model used in the calculations; in the 1:100 scale, the total ship length L_{SFS2} is equal to 1.387 m. (b) Domain decomposition in multiple levels of refinement, shown in the center-plane of the ship. The different colors correspond to the seven levels of refinement used in the calculation. The inset shows the refined blocks close to the ship surface.

The computational domain has been taken equal to $15.5 L_{SFS2}$ along the x streamwise direction and $4.98 L_{SFS2}$ ($2.2 L_{SFS2}$) along the y (z) directions, being L_{SFS2} the ship length equal to 1.387 m in the 1:100 model. Despite not shown here, we have verified that flow results presented in the following are converged w.r.t. the computational domain size. The simulated flow is characterized by a Reynolds number of $5.4 \cdot 10^5$, computed on the basis of the ship beam width b equal to 0.1371 meters and assuming a headwind free-stream velocity of $57.5 \frac{m}{s}$. The surface of the ship is modelled via no-slip boundary conditions implemented through bounce-back approach, while the walls of the computational domain have been treated via the same boundary conditions adopted in the sphere case in Section 1.1. An important practical remark is that at the inflow the Ladd's correction term has been evaluated fixing the density to one (in lattice units)[41], as we have noticed that nearest-neighbor interpolation of the density from the first layer of inner cells in the domain produces numerical spurious noise. The inflow velocity has been set to 0.06 in lattice units and the domain has been meshed with a nonuniform grid with seven levels of refinement: the corresponding domain decomposition is shown in Figure 3b. With this meshing strategy, the used grid contains $0.3671 \cdot 10^9$ cells partitioned in 18432 blocks, with a near-wall sampling of 0.00075 m; **the calculations have been performed on six GPU nodes, each equipped with four Nvidia-A100 GPU cards**. A total physical simulation time of 6.0 seconds has been chosen and the time averaged velocity magnitude has been computed sampling \mathbf{u} in the last second of simulation.

The obtained results are summarized in Figure 4. In Figure 4a, we present the time-averaged velocity magnitude normalized by the free-stream velocity in the centerplane of the ship: the flow topology is well captured by our calculation, with the location of the average reattachment point ⁶ at about 49 % of the ship deck length, in agreement with the full scale results provided by Forrest and Owen[42]. Additionally, our flow profile agrees quantitatively with the results obtained via Delayed-Detached Eddy Simulation provided by Fernandez and collaborators (see Figure 6b of Ref.[43] for comparison). Figure 4b shows a snapshot of the instantaneous velocity field behind the funnel and on the ship deck, revealing the highly turbulent character of the developed flow at the considered Reynolds number.

To quantitatively validate the accuracy provided by RR-BGK coupled with SISM subgrid model, we compare the computed mean flow velocity probed along specific lines above the ship deck with experimental data obtained in wind tunnel experiments. These lines have been considered at 25 % and 50 % of the deck length downstream from the hangar and at fixed z , chosen equal to the hangar height. Results for velocities along these lines are displayed in Fig-

⁶Here the reattachment point is defined as the position along the streamwise direction where the x -component of the velocity changes sign along the deck.

ure 4c and 4d respectively. These locations are conceptually relevant as they probe the region above the ship deck where helicopter's rotor operates during landing manoeuvres. Experimental data in Figure 4c have been taken from Syms[44], while those shown in Figure 4d are from Yuan *et al.* [45]. We note that Syms only provides u_x data and in this case the experiment is performed at a slightly higher free-stream velocity ($60.0 \frac{m}{s}$) than the one considered here, which reproduces the experimental conditions of Ref.[45].

Figure 4: Main results of the simulation of SFS2 ship airwake with RR-BGK coupled with SISIM subgrid model. Calculations are performed on the SFS2 model in headwind conditions, considering a Reynolds number of $5.4 \cdot 10^5$, computed w.r.t. the ship beam length. The domain is sampled with a nonuniform cartesian mesh, with seven levels of refinement. (a) Time-average velocity magnitude normalized by free-stream velocity in the center plane of the ship. (b) Instantaneous velocity magnitude at the end of the simulation ($t = 6.0s$) behind the ship funnel and on the flight deck surface. (c) Stream-wise velocity component at 25 % deck length and at hangar height compared with experimental data from Ref. [44]. (d) Same as (c) but probing both u_x and u_y velocity components at half deck length, compared with experimental data from Ref. [45]. In (c) and (d) the horizontal axis represents spatial positions along y , normalized by the beam length, i.e. the width of the ship.

In both probe locations, we observe a significant reduction of the streamwise velocity in proximity of the ship centerline (i.e. close to $y = 0.0$); additionally, our calculations seem to properly reproduce the slight asymmetric profile of the x -component of the velocity, as found in experimental data and by Syms's LBM-calculations, but not reproduced in DES simulations presented in Refs.[42][45]. Overall, we find a rather satisfactory agreement between experimental data and our calculation. In particular, the agreement is excellent for the u_y component of the velocity (dashed blue line in Figure 4d) in the middle of the flight deck, while a slight underestimation of the streamwise velocity close to ship centerline is observed at both locations along the deck, although this discrepancy is only marginal at 25% of the deck length while it is more pronounced in the deck center.

The presented results demonstrate the capability of the implemented approach to effectively simulate this type of flows. We also point out that we have attempted to model these high-Re flow conditions with BGK collision model coupled to static Smagorinsky subgrid viscosity but we were not able to obtain reasonable results because of the relevant stability issues associated with this collision model.

3 First optimizations of waLBerla code to improve performance on GPU hardware

The usage of nonuniform grids with multiple levels of refinement is mandatory in the simulation of turbulent flows with LBM to obtain a sufficient spatial discretization in domain regions where high resolution is needed (e.g. close to solid walls) while limiting the size of the cartesian mesh to be processed during the calculation.

Clearly, the adoption of nonuniform grids makes the LBM algorithm more complicated than its uniform-mesh counterpart, as the multi-level character of the sampling introduce the additional problem of communication and synchronization between neighboring cells belonging to different levels of refinement. In waLBerla, grid refinement is based on the approach proposed by Rohde[46][47], where cells are assumed in the center of each mesh voxel and the domain is decomposed via 2:1 octree-balanced partitioning where blocks of refinement level l can only have neighbors on the same level (equal-level communication), on level $l + 1$ (coarse-to-fine communication) or belonging to level $l - 1$ (fine-to-coarse communication)[48].

To communicate the PDFs between neighboring blocks, a pack-unpack procedure is adopted[48][49]. In the packing step, the values of the f_i on the sender block are collected into a buffer array while in the unpacking phase these data are read from the buffer array and written in the ghost cells of the receiver block; this procedure is common to communication between both local (i.e. assigned to the same MPI task) and non-local (i.e. assigned to different MPI tasks) pairs of blocks, while the details about how the pack-unpack step is performed depend on the communication type (equal level, fine to coarse, coarse to fine) and will not be discussed in the following.

This pack-unpack step is presently performed directly on the GPU, using GPU kernels obtained through the flexible code-generation functionality provided by waLBerla[24]. To better understand the procedure followed by waLBerla, we consider the coarse to fine communication between levels l and $l + 1$, without loss of generality. In this case, for each block on level l , neighboring blocks on level $l + 1$ are identified together with their sender-to-receiver communication direction; packing kernels copy data from the l -block to a buffer while unpacking kernels operate on the $l + 1$ -receiving block, as soon as data are received. We remark here that these steps are performed at each timestep during the simulation. This implies that a packing-kernel and an unpacking-kernel are called for each pair of neighboring blocks in the domain: in the case of a large number of refinement levels, this procedure causes the launch of a large number of small functions running on the GPU, without fully making use of the available hardware resources.

In this context, we have started investigating optimisation techniques which could reduce the weight of this pack-unpack step in the overall simulation time. Despite a complete analysis of scaling and performance of waLBerla being beyond the scope of this document, here we present the first steps performed in this code-optimization activity. As we are interested in static grid refinement (i.e. in a mesh not changing with time), at the beginning of the simulation we determine for each block its neighbors and we save to disk the locations on the PDFs arrays from which taking f_i values in the packing phase and to which writing data in the unpacking step. These information are therefore computed only once as a pre-processing step before starting the simulation.

After this, we have re-organized the way in which pack-unpack kernels are called in the application, carrying out an extensive GPU-kernel fusion procedure. Taking again as example the coarse to fine communication, we have selected all pairs of $(l, l + 1)$ blocks in the domain communicating along a direction \mathbf{d} of the D3Q19 stencil used in the calculation, then we have defined a single pair of pack-unpack GPU kernels which is responsible for the communication of the data exchanged by all pairs of blocks which are neighbors along the direction \mathbf{d} and belong to l and $l + 1$ levels. In this way, the number of functions called on the GPU is dramatically reduced, as we have now one kernel per direction instead of one device function called for each block pair; furthermore, as each GPU-kernel performs more work, the hardware turns out to be better utilized. Clearly, exactly the same operations have been carried out for the other types of communications.

To test the effect of these modifications, we have performed calculations on the SFS2 model with 5, 6 and 7 levels of refinement on eight GPUs, considering physical conditions analogous to those discussed in Section 2.1, but halving both the total number of timesteps and the domain sizes along directions orthogonal to the one of the main flow; we also note that in all calculations presented below, each domain block contains a mesh of [32, 44, 30] cells.

In Figure 5, we present the speedup of the modified version[50] w.r.t. to the original code for the different levels of refinement considered in these calculations. More precisely, the speedup has been computed as the ratio between the total simulation time of the original code and the total execution time of the optimized version. It is possible to notice that the implemented modifications provide an important speedup to the code, which increases with the number of considered levels of refinement. This result is rationalized by the fact that the higher the number of levels the larger will be the number of blocks in the domain and, consequently, also the number of pack-unpack steps performed at each timestep; therefore an improved pack-unpack scheme will offer a more and more relevant speedup.

These promising results motivate us to keep on working on code analysis and optimisation on GPU, in order to enable the usage of large number of refinement levels to get the correct near-wall sampling needed in LES calculations at high Re.

Figure 5: Speedup of walBer1a code obtained by optimization of the pack-unpack procedure used in inter-block communication, for different numbers of refinement levels. The speedup is here defined as the ratio between the total simulation time of the original code and the total execution time of the optimized version, once fixing the number of refinement levels in the domain in the case of interest. The optimized version permits to achieve a speedup larger than a factor of three once six and seven levels of refinement are considered. Details about the chosen test-case, parallelization and the implemented code optimizations are provided in the main text.

4 Conclusions and outlook

In this report, we discussed the progress done so far to improve `waLBer1a` capabilities in the treatment of highly turbulent flows in a computationally efficient way on heterogeneous hardware.

The theory and implementation of RR-BGK collision model has been presented in detail, to demonstrate its capability to increase numerical stability of classical BGK while keeping high numerical efficiency. The accuracy provided by this model has been extensively tested on low and medium Re simple flows to validate its current implementation in `waLBer1a` package. In this context, we plan to complete RR-BGK implementation by extending the collision model to include the action of external forces on the flow, in order to enable the simulation of rotating obstacles via simplified (but efficient) disk/line actuator models.

We have then combined RR-BGK with `SISM` subgrid model, which was not available in `waLBer1a` before this work. Once compared with the widely used `SM` model, `SISM` is able to mitigate its near-wall excessive dissipation while keeping unaltered the ease of implementation in a BGK-like collision which characterizes `SM` subgrid model. This coupled implementation has been applied to simulate the turbulent air-wake behind a `SFS2` ship model in head-wind conditions. Our results confirm the remarkable stability of this RR-BGK-`SISM` collision model even at very large Re , while an accurate comparison with experimental data and other `CFD` calculations has demonstrated the good physical description of such turbulent flows. In the near future we will focus on a better understanding of the observed discrepancies between experimental data and `LBM` results. One possible reason could be the way in which the low-frequency strain rate $\langle \mathbf{S} \rangle$ is presently computed, i.e. via a direct time-average procedure. In the near future, we will explore the `SISM` model based on Kalman filtering technique and we will evaluate the feasibility of its implementation within `waLBer1a` architecture.

Another possible reason of the observed discrepancies in Section 2.1 could be the insufficient near wall sampling used in the calculation. In practice, the usage of meshes with a higher number of refinement levels (ideally 9-10 refinement levels) is mandatory to solve this issue, as demonstrated by the cartesian grids already used in `LBM` calculations of Landing-Gear-Noise performed with the commercial code `PowerFlow`[51].

The efficient usage of `waLBer1a` with this kind of meshes requires an intense activity in terms of code optimization along the line of what discussed in Section 3. This topic will be the main focus of our work in the next months, trying as a first step, to generalise the presented kernel fusion process to other steps in the calculation, like the stream-collide algorithm, which is presently carried out separately for each block in the domain.

Finally, in the longer term, we plan to investigate the possibility of including the presented implementations in the code-generation functionality of `waLBer1a`, making the usage of the presented code more flexible and user-friendly.

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References

Acronyms used

HPC	High Performance Computing
LBM	Lattice Boltzmann Method
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
PDFs	Particle Distribution Functions
Re	Reynolds
Kn	Knusden
GLUPS	Giga Lattice Updates Per Second
LES	Large Eddy Simulations
SM	Smagorinsky
SISM	Shear Improved SMagorinsky model
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
SFS2	Simple Frigate Shape 2

Software mentioned

waLBerla Widely Applicable Lattice Boltzmann solver from ERLAngen

URLs referenced

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